

ReCreate
Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

Halonen et al.

**National implementation
differences of norms applicable
to reuse in ReCreate's pilots**

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Abstract

The ReCreate project researches reusing precast concrete elements, not originally designed for disassembly, through real-life deconstruction and reuse pilots in four European countries. This report shows what reuse in practice faces in terms of legislation and regulation. The firms in the piloting countries (Finland, Sweden, Germany and the Netherlands) have had country-specific experiences, but there are also common themes, which are partly related to the EU policy background. The experiences with current legislation and policies are distilled into policy recommendations, which cover shared themes and country-specific issues.

The pilots in Finland, Sweden, Germany and the Netherlands operated in the current regulatory environment. The benefit of this setup is that challenges to circular construction that come from regulation become highlighted as problems to be solved according to the requirements of the existing regulatory environment. In Finland, the major challenge was to determine whether the reclaimed concrete elements were waste or not, with related environmental permitting issues regarding storage. Following deliberations with local and national authorities, the Ministry of the Environment provided clear instructions as to how to determine the waste status of reclaimed prefabricated concrete elements. In the permitting process, the so-called site-specific building permit process was until now untested for reclaimed prefabricated concrete elements. Also in this case, extensive discussions were held with local authorities to ensure a smooth process. Key to this was the emphasis on technical documentation related to quality assurance. Finally, in the Finnish case local land policy and land allocation processes were shown to be a significant potential incentive. ReCreate facilitated discussions and workshops, through which a new plot allocation competition model was developed, which was successfully tested by the City of Tampere.

In Sweden, the waste status of reclaimed prefabricated concrete elements has been an issue as well. Unlike in Finland, there is currently no clear path to preventing these products from being interpreted as waste, as the interpretation of regulations has not yet been sufficiently developed. The major issue in the Swedish case, however, is the liability of the developer for fulfilling the property's legal requirements. In practice, this has meant quality assurance testing, ensuring indoor air quality, and complying with REACH legislation. In Sweden, no comprehensive guidance on these issues is presently available. Finally, permitting issues are a future concern for which conclusive, practical guidance has yet to be developed. The Swedish deconstruction pilot project was concluded before the introduction of new requirements, but it pointed to challenges to identify products and materials available for reclamation. This aspect could be remedied by amending the requirements for a 'control plan', which is a part of the demolition permit that indicates how building materials could be reused.

In the Netherlands too, the waste status of the recovered elements is an issue. However, it is currently unclear whether the waste status will be formally determined. The Netherlands has a comprehensive self-assessment tool, which companies can use to determine whether materials or products are likely waste, non-waste, or require an End-of-Waste process. The tool produces information that local authorities can use in permitting processes. In theory, there are many authorities that could potentially assess the waste status. However, the Dutch pilot has no experience with this yet. Based on previous projects, the project partners indicate that quality assurance and technical characteristics are most important for the assessment of construction plans for the purpose of acquiring a building permit. To this end, the Dutch project partners have also frequently discussed with local authorities about permit requirements.

In the German case, the waste status is relatively clearly defined in law, but the challenge comes from the point of view of ownership of materials. In the pilot project, this aspect was emphasised by negotiations on liability of a non-project actor. Although the waste status is in principle clear, it is also connected to quality assurance issues. Currently, in the German case, it is unclear which public authority will decide on this issue for the German reuse pilot. This issue is nonetheless important for acquiring a building permit. In this case, either local or state-level authorities could be the decision-makers, but either authority has its own regulation-based paths to quality assurance.

Taken as a whole, the experience from these four countries therefore shows that in practice, the waste status issue, quality assurance issues and how to include these in permitting processes are common challenges to all pilot projects. There are a few country-specific observations, like the qualification of designers active in circular construction (Finland), producer responsibility (Sweden and Germany), and the potential synergies of climate policy incentives and reuse (Sweden), which can nevertheless contribute learnings to other contexts as well.

Based on the experience of the four pilot countries, it is recommended that regulation around the waste status is clarified on the EU level. More clarification regarding technical assessment should be given too: it is important for companies to know what rules apply, also regarding liabilities. On a national level, there should be clarity regarding permitting processes to enable scaling up reuse. Removing such regulatory hurdles is a start, but public incentives are also needed to accelerate the transition to circular construction.

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1. Introduction

This report is the second of a set of two ReCreate deliverables that are linked to the necessary public policy change if the EU construction sector is to be transitioned from linear to circular. The current report explores how the EU, national and local level regulations presented in the first report (Halonen et al., 2024) have been interpreted by authorities in the context of ReCreate's pilots and how they have, thus, guided reuse in practice.

The main goal of the report is to provide a practical outlook into the issues that companies or other actors in the ReCreate piloting countries (Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany) should consider as part of their construction processes involving reused construction products. The report also examines if any current regulations, administrative practices or interpretations constitute barriers for reuse. As a result, an assessment of how norms should be further developed to promote the circular economy is delivered at the end of the report.

The findings of the previous report lay the foundations for the analyses in the current report. The empirical experiences from the pilots were analysed through the legal frameworks identified in Halonen et al. (2024). The frameworks guided the analyses and for each pilot, questions such as the following were asked:

- how did a specific statute or the issues it regulates come into play in the pilots,
- what kind of debates did it generate among stakeholders in the pilots, and
- what impact did it have in practice?

Furthermore, the document also elaborates on regulatory interpretations that were developed further during the project. Like the first report, this document does not go through all regulation-related issues of the construction sector but focuses on those that have generated debate or had a practical impact on the progress of ReCreate's pilots and reuse more generally.

The current report takes mainly a national focus for the analyses. This is because, as analysed in previous report (Halonen et al. 2024), the most relevant regulations for reuse are presently in national control. Nevertheless, the report's observations also feed the further development of EU-level regulation, such as the Waste Framework Directive, or Construction Products Regulation (CPR). It is important to ensure that by the time the CPR's transition period ends in 2040, the CPR and associated regulations (e.g. harmonised standards) will not repeat the hurdles encountered in the pilots under the national legislation but will fully address and resolve them. During the CPR's 15-year transition period (until 2040), it is important to ensure regulation at national, regional, and local levels is also developed, so as not to hinder or halt the mainstreaming of circular construction, including reuse of precast concrete elements.

The report is divided into two main parts. The first part (Chapters 2-5) discusses, country by country, how the regulations and other norms were faced during the pilots. The chapters elaborate on how different matters were interpreted in practice by the authorities, which matters caused ambiguities in each country, and how such ambiguities were resolved. The discussion will focus exclusively on the issues that differed from the usual industrial practices in each country. The second part (Chapter 6) presents proposals to improve norms and administrative practices based on the insights gathered from the pilots. The report ends with a concluding discussion (Chapter 7) that summarises the key insights.

2. Finland

In Finland, three issues raised debate during the ReCreate project: the waste status of deconstructed building components (Section 2.1); product approval and conducting a 'construction site specific' approval in practice (Section 2.2), and local land policies, such as land allocation competitions as incentives for circular development (Section 2.3).

2.1. Waste status of reclaimed elements

As discussed in Halonen et al. (2024: 10–12), waste status is one of the key regulatory topics in Finland related to reuse of building components. The debate has focused on the question whether deconstructed building components, such as concrete elements, are to be considered waste. In discussions, companies inside and outside of ReCreate have pointed out the matter is significant to them. If deconstructed building components are labelled as waste without exception, their reuse would involve time- and resource-consuming administrative processes (e.g. End-of-Waste [EoW]) described in Halonen et al. (2024: 12), the outcome of which can presently be unpredictable. From a pure business point of view, this makes investing into reusing building components less attractive to companies. Consequently, a reasonable and justified stance on the waste question is highly important for scaling up reuse, including the ReCreate solutions, in the construction sector.

As also discussed in Halonen et al. (2024: 11–12), ReCreate's Finnish pilot's elements initially received a waste status from the environmental protection authority (*ympäristöviranomaisen*) in 2023. However, the authority acknowledged that there were uncertainties related to the basis of the decision, and it would be beneficial to have further discourse on the matter. As a result, ReCreate's Finnish partners initiated a working group and begun to facilitate discussions involving representatives from the project; the environmental protection authority; the Ministry of the Environment (*ympäristöministeriö*); the regional authority, Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (*ELY-keskus*); and the governmental research institute, Finnish Environmental Institute (*SYKE*), with the aim to bring a clarification to the matter.

The discussions held over nine months helped to structure the issues at stake and started to build consensus between the actors involved. However, despite the constructive discourse, a great deal of ambiguities and different interpretations remained. For example, some parties argued that the starting point must always be that any kind of building decommissioning activity, including deconstruction of whole parts, produces waste because otherwise the quality and further use of the parts cannot be controlled. The perspective generated counterarguments from other actors, emphasising that demolition and deconstruction are qualitatively different. The goal of the demolition is to remove building parts from use, while the aim of deconstruction is to reclaimed parts for further use; reusability is ensured as per the construction legislation (see Halonen et al. 2024: 40, and Chapter 2.2.).

In the light of the remaining ambiguities, ReCreate's Finnish partners, together with the local environmental authority responsible for the pilot's case, decided to seek a formal statement from the Ministry of Environment. It is noteworthy here that the policy request did not take, for example, a legislative approach, but a practical and problem-focused one. This was a deliberate decision because based on the previous discourse, the legislation was *per se* open to interpretation. Had the response to the policy request not been connected to a real-life context and problem-setting, it would likely not have offered useful arguments. The approach paid off, as the response addressed all the main problem areas, as follows¹:

General clarification

In general, the policy response takes a stance that reclaimed building components do not automatically become waste as a result of deconstruction. The decisive factor is the preservation of the building product in a usable state throughout the deconstruction and reuse process. If at any stage of the process, for one reason or another, parts become unusable, only then they become waste. Thus, the policy response delegates a lot of responsibility on the matter to companies but leaves room for the authorities to intervene in case there is justified doubt about the quality of the process or the components.

The argument is an important aspect of the policy response. A clear distinction between a conventional demolition process and a deconstruction process acts as the basis to consider the implications of waste legislation separately.

Clarifications to the Waste act (646/2011)² Section 5§

Section 5 of the Waste Act lays down the terms and conditions for activities that fall under the Waste Act, defining that 'waste means any substance or object that the holder discards, intends to discard or is required to discard.' The policy response clarifies that, in the case of reused building components, dismantling and reuse plans done in advance (before the deconstruction) serves as an indicator that the holder does not intend to discard the objects.

Furthermore, the policy response offers clarifications also to Section 5a, which lays down four requirements that must be fulfilled in order for a substance or an object not to be waste:

- 1) "Further use of the substance or object is certain";
 - This was one of the main topics causing ambiguity in the previous discourse. Originally, the local environmental authority suggested that a street address for the reuse site would serve as an indicator for the certainty of further use, as meant in section of the law. However, in practice there are various issues with this. Only rarely is the physical address of the upcoming building, where the reuse will take place, known at the time of the deconstruction, when the decision regarding the waste status is made. From a business point of view, it is

¹ At the time of writing this document, the statement is not yet publicly available. However, it can be requested from the ReCreate coordinator, Satu Huuhka, or directly from Ministry of the Environment.

² <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/2011/20110646>

problematic if already at the time of dismantling, every deconstructed component should be assigned to a specific new building.

- The policy response suggests that a street address is not reasonable information to require, but certainty of further use can be ensured through three conditions. First, the aim is to reclaim products that are in general demand (construction products). Second, the reclamation activities are systematic and organised. Third, the reclamation activities are more costly than a conventional demolition (the higher cost renders it unlikely that an actor would try to avoid waste management responsibilities under the guise of reuse).
- 2) "The substance or object can be used directly, as is, or without any further processing other than normal industrial practice";
- In the previous discourse, some parties found it difficult to clearly determine what kind of processing or modification would fall within the limits of normal industrial practice. For example, how much can an element be cut, or can new surface coatings be added, etc.
 - The policy response clarified that such processing practices and modifications are normal that can also be carried out on new elements. Sometimes, for example due to a production mistake or a last-minute change in design, new elements may have to be modified after their production. Thus, such modifications should be considered as normal industrial practice in the case of reused components, too.
- 3) "The substance or object is produced as an integral part of a production process";
- This point did not require any clarifications as it is clear that reclaimed building components are produced as an integral part of a deconstruction process and are not, for example, byproducts of such processes.
- 4) "The substance or object fulfils all relevant product requirements as well as environmental and health protection requirements for the specific use and, when assessed overall, its use will not endanger or harm health or the environment".
- This is one of the key issues the authorities were concerned about regarding the reuse of building components, since they must be certain that no hazardous materials begin to circulate uncontrollably in the society.
 - The policy response suggests that this matter is under control for two reasons. First, the high cost of deconstruction (compared to demolition) does not encourage operators to carry out deconstruction projects simply to avoid waste treatment costs. Second, the quality of reclaimed building components must be ensured in accordance with construction regulation before the construction of a new building (see Halonen et al. 2024: 40, and Chapter 2.2.). Together, these matters make the circulation of hazardous materials highly unlikely. Moreover,

as already mentioned, authorities always have the possibility to intervene if they have doubt about the safety and legality of the activity.

Clarifications for the Waste act (646/2011) Section 6§

Section 6 defines the key terms of the Act, one of which is reuse, defined as 'using a product or its component again for same the purpose for which it was originally conceived'. The policy response specified that in the construction sector, reuse means that a reclaimed construction product can be used as any type of construction product. For example, given that technical requirements are met, a deconstructed slab can be reused as an outdoor element, or a load-bearing wall can be reused as a non-load-bearing element. Although the clarification may sound as semantic only, in practice it is highly useful for the development of circular solutions. During the preceding discussion, arguments were made that reclaimed products should only be allowed to be used for exactly the same purpose as before. This kind of limitation could have potentially made reuse possibilities very rigid and uncreative.

Conclusion

With the policy response, the Ministry of the Environment was able to clarify most, if not all, substantial ambiguities related to the matter in Finland. The response provided support for the local authorities to re-examine interpretations of the waste legislation. In the case of ReCreate's Finnish pilot, this led to the local environmental authority to reconsider and remove the waste status of the ReCreate elements. This decision also ceased the EoW process that had already started.

It is noteworthy that although the Ministry's policy response is not legally binding and does not hold power over the decision making of local environmental authorities, the authorities must now consider its arguments. If, in the future, an authority grants a waste status for reclaimed building components, justifications must be provided against the points raised by the Ministry of the Environment. Therefore, the statement is of value not only for ReCreate's Finnish pilot, but also for the Finnish circular construction industry as a whole.

2.1.1. Environmental permits in storage and refurbishment

Another, more specific matter related to the waste status was discussed during the Finnish pilot, too: what kind of (environmental) permit, if any, do storage and refurbishment works of reclaimed building components require? The ReCreate partner, Consolis Parma, that is responsible for storing and refurbishing the components, already had an environmental permit for normal company operations as a concrete element manufacturer. However, it was not clear whether reused components could be handled under the same permit or if the permit should e.g. be amended. The matter would have been clearer if the components had been considered as waste, since regulation on handling waste materials is explicit. However, as the components' waste status was eventually cancelled, the matter required further clarification.

To clarify the matter, the local environmental authority was consulted. The authority clarified that in principle, storing and refurbishing reclaimed building components, which

are not considered as waste, does not require an environmental permit. This is because Attachment 1³ of the Environmental Protection Act (*ympäristönsuojelulaki 527/2014*)⁴ explicitly lists all operations requiring a permit. The only listed operation, which could in some way be associated with storage and refurbishment works of non-waste reclaimed components, is operating a concrete factory. However, since the permit requirement of concrete factories is based on the production of new concrete and the environmental risks associated with it, the authority does not believe that it would apply on storage or refurbishment works of such components.

In other situations, the permit can be required due to so-called 'general authorisation requirements' laid down in the Environmental Protection Act. For example, if an operation produces noise or dust in amounts that disturbs the neighbours, a permit is required. The authority saw it as unlikely that this requirement would come into play when storing and refurbishing reused components. Although not mentioned by the environmental authority, the risk is further reduced by the fact that sites and facilities suitable for such activities are located in districts zoned specifically for industrial purposes in urban plans, i.e. well away from functions that could be disturbed by the activity, such as residential areas.

Although the viewpoint was not raised during the discussions with the authority, refurbishment of elements will produce small amounts of waste materials (cut-offs) and wastewater (e.g., if pressure washing is used), which must be properly managed. Therefore, although the storage and refurbishment of reclaimed components does not *per se* seem to require an environmental permit, a party intending to carry out such activities in the future should have detailed prior discussions with the authorities before proceeding to ensure compliance with environmental regulation.

2. 2. Construction site specific product approval process in practice

In Finland, product approval of reused construction products is obtained through a 'construction site specific approval' process in conjunction with the building permit application process (see Halonen et al. 2024: 40). However, there is no prior experience of this process in the case of reused products. For this reason, Finnish ReCreate partners held preliminary discussions and negotiations with building supervision authorities so that by the time permits would be applied for the Finnish pilots, there would already be a principled consensus about the process and involved documentation. Discussions were carried out with building inspectors of the City of Tampere, where the first pilots are located. Additionally, Finnish ReCreate partners presented the topic several times to the carbon footprint and circularity task force of the national network of building supervisors ('TopTen')

³ <https://www.finlex.fi/data/sdliite/liite/6410.pdf>

⁴ <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/2014/20140527>

to disseminate information and encourage discussions in other municipalities, too, and facilitate the establishment of joint practices.

The meetings sought opinion on and confirmation for the quality assurance and product approval proposal of ReCreate (see Halonen et al., 2024, and Räsänen et al., 2024). Generally speaking, the reception was good and, most importantly, the local authorities also confirmed in the formal preliminary consultations that the pilot can proceed as proposed. The local authority did not have an inherent, detailed view on how quality assurance should be carried out in practice. The main purpose of the process is to help the inspector determine that the reclaimed building components are technically suitable for the intended use and will not harm humans or the environment. In practice, this takes place through technical documentation about tests and inspections, which are provided to the inspector when applying for the building permit. In the ReCreate pilot's case, the documentation was produced as a focal part of the project. However, in future, practitioners should pay attention to the extent and quality of the required documentation⁵.

When the documents were ready, the construction site specific approval process was in practice almost like a normal building permit application process; The test and other reports were attached to the permit application. Practically the only matter that required additional clarifications was the expected service life of the reused components in comparison to new ones. The information was provided, and as there was no significant difference in the time that it took to receive the permit, the matter did not hinder or delay the permit application process.

The preliminary discussions and negotiations were a crucial part of the process, as they helped to co-determine with the authorities that the reused products and the upcoming building are safe and sound. The construction site specific approval process is much more interactive process compared to the 'normal' process, where established standards and practices can be applied. Consequently, creating trust and understanding between the parties is much more important here, and open and frequent communication as well as the involvement of the authority are key tools for achieving this (on this, see also Jonker-Hoffrén, 2023). If the authority considers that it has not been adequately informed or that the company applying for a permit is not sharing focal information, even if it was not the company's intention to conceal anything, the permit process would likely be more difficult because the company and its activities would not look transparent enough to the authority. In this light, it is not very surprising that the authority itself also repeatedly encouraged to be in contact as early as possible.

⁵ It is noteworthy that in exploring the correct extent for such documentation, a research project like ReCreate may actually produce excessive testing documents, much more so than may be needed once the practice is established. During preliminary discussion, some authorities shared this view. Thus, most likely, practitioners in future building projects need not assume they must carry out tests identical to ReCreate. Instead of the testing schemes implemented for ReCreate's pilots, they should refer to ReCreate's best practice proposal for quality assurance, which will be published later as a deliverable (D4.3).

2. 3. Local land policies and land allocation competitions as incentives

As discussed in Halonen et al. (2024: 56), local land policies and land allocation competitions are gaining a foothold in supporting the circular economy transition of the construction industry in Finland. They are increasingly recognised as public policy tools to incentivise companies to develop circular economy solutions. A handful of competitions have already been organized previously, though they are not yet enough to put in motion larger changes in the industry. This requires more systematic repetition of policy actions in multiple municipalities.

To help the municipalities to begin utilising circularity-themed land allocation competitions more systematically, ReCreate project member City of Tampere organised and facilitated a working group, with the goal to devise unified circularity criteria for land allocation competitions for the municipalities. The working group consisted of circa 25 experts working in the 10 largest and most circularity-oriented municipalities in Finland. The group started its work in early 2023, and the criteria were published in February 2024. In 2023, two workshops were organised to gather feedback from stakeholders. The first one was aimed at the industry members (investors, construction companies, consultants etc.), and the second one was directed at municipalities. Although the events were organised for highly specific audiences, altogether as many as 110 experts attended. The criteria were published in an open national seminar, arranged in the collaboration with a publicly-owned circular economy development platform 'Kiertotalous Pirkanmaa' (Circular Tampere Region).

The platform was one of the main collaborators in developing criteria. To ensure the criteria will be available and findable after the ReCreate project, the latest version of the criteria can be found on the platform's website (also in English)⁶. The published materials encompass also detailed instructions for organising a competition. In a nutshell, competitors choose which target level they can commit to and receive points according to the ambition level. Most of the criteria are quantitative, but there are also a few qualitative criteria, the achievement of which is evaluated by the competition organiser. The applicant with the most points wins the competition and can purchase or rent the land.

It is worth to note that the criteria do not include minimum requirements. Consequently, the implementation risks for competition organisers (municipalities) are minimal, as they do not have to worry that no one will apply due to too demanding requirements. Indeed, in a purely competitive setting, the participating companies can set their own targets within the limits of their own risk assessment, ensuring that the ambitiousness of the circular solutions remains reasonable from company economic and implementation perspective. At the same time, the competition nevertheless encourages markets to propose more ambitious

⁶ <https://kiertotalouspirkanmaa.fi/en/materiaalipankki/circular-economy-criteria-for-land-allocation/>

circular solutions, as the goal of all the applicants is to offer better solutions than the competitors in order to win the plot.

Some examples of the criteria are given below, and the full competition framework is available online⁶.

Examples of quantitative criteria

Example 1: The carbon footprint of construction materials and products to be used in the buildings is XX % smaller than in the reference calculation (a building with business-as-usual solutions and materials) [kgCO₂e] (choose from the drop-down menu). Verification through carbon footprint calculations.⁷

- <10% 0 points
- 10–20% 4 points
- 20–40% 12 points
- >40% 20 points

Example 2: A minimum of X kg (choose from the drop-down menu) of reused concrete building components are utilised in the buildings.

- not utilized at all 0 points
- 5000 kg⁸ 4 points
- 25 000 kg 12 points
- 50 000 kg 20 points

Example 3: A minimum of X kg (choose from the drop-down menu) of reused building components made from materials other than concrete are utilised in the buildings.

- not utilized at all 0 points
- 500 kg⁹ 4 points
- 1000 kg 12 points
- 5000 kg 20 points

⁷ Emissions during phases A1–A5 [kgCO₂e] are to be included in the calculations of embodied carbon. Carbon footprint calculations are compiled in accordance with the principles of 'Method for the whole life carbon assessment of buildings' by the Finnish Ministry of the Environment (2019), including life cycles A1–A5. The calculations and report on the calculations must be based on the clarifications by the City of Helsinki (2019; in Finnish) where appropriate for the aforementioned life cycles.

Additional clarifications:

- In the carbon footprint calculations, the carbon footprint for product phases (A1–A3) of reusable building components is set as 0 % of a new building component's carbon footprint.
- The plot allocator reserves the right to publish all carbon calculations.
- The plot allocator reserves the right to validate the proposed carbon calculations if the calculations presented by different actors are not mutually comparable. Possible comparisons are performed by a third party on two tenderers with the highest total score.

⁸ The target levels scale is based on calculations made on the presumption on the average weight of a single hollow-core slab (5,000kg).

⁹ The target levels scale is based on calculations made on the presumption that 50 m² of bricks weigh about 8,000kg; 120m² of corrugated steel sheet weighs about 1,000kg).

Example 4: The reported building components have been designed for disassembly (choose from the drop-down menu).¹⁰

- | | |
|---|-----------|
| • none | 0 points |
| • structures other than load-bearing frames | 4 points |
| • load-bearing frames | 12 points |
| • all structures, including load-bearing ones | 20 points |

An example of the qualitative criteria

Example 5: The proposed circular economy solutions have XX novelty value (assessed by the competition organiser) on the Finnish market.¹¹

- | | |
|---|-----------|
| • no or low novelty value | 0 points |
| • clear novelty value | 12 points |
| • exceptionally significant novelty value | 20 points |

Conclusion

All major Finnish cities have committed to promote circular construction but there is a need to develop tools that help cities in this task. The criteria developed and their functionality have received highly positive feedback from public authorities, and many cities have shown interest in adopting them in future land allocation competitions. Currently, at least one Finnish city is in the process of implementing them. Hopefully the future will see more replication of the criteria, because the most significant impact for the industry will come from the systematic repetition of policy actions.

¹⁰ Structures refer to walls, ceilings, roofs/floors, pillars, or beams. This criterion does not, therefore, consider elements such as windows or building service systems. At least 80 percent of the entire framework must be reusable in order to report the chosen structures in the answer.

The criterion is verified with a reuse report that must be delivered as part of the implementation plans. The report must include a description of joints used in the structures and instruction for disassembling, transportation, and installation of the components.

¹¹ 'Novelty value on the Finnish market' indicates that the proposed solution does not have references in the construction sector in Finland. Fewer references denote more points.

3. Sweden

In February 2022, the Swedish government assigned the National Board of housing, building and planning (*Boverket*) to develop the transition to a circular economy in the construction sector¹². Boverket finalised their work and reported it to the government the 20th of December 2024 (Boverket, 2024) The needs pertain to three main topics: the waste status of reused components (Section 3.1), the developer's responsibility for property requirements of building solutions (Section 3.2), and reuse inventories connected to demolition permits (Section 3.3).

3.1. Waste status of reclaimed elements

ReCreate's Swedish reuse pilot was a temporary pavilion, used during the city expo H22 in Helsingborg. After the expo, the pavilion was disassembled and the concrete elements were transported to a storage site, with the ambition to reuse the elements once again in a new building project. The process after that raised concerns in the Swedish country cluster with regard to scaling up reuse of concrete elements. Since there was no immediate recipient or intended use for the concrete elements, it was judged that the elements were to be seen as waste and thereby fell under the waste legislation. The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) indicated that deconstructed concrete elements could be viewed similarly as excavation masses, and thus the determination of the waste status could follow their guidance on excavation masses¹³. The guidance states *'If it is ensured that there is use for the masses within a reasonable period of time, this is a circumstance that speaks for the masses not being waste'*. According to the Swedish Environmental Code (1998:808)¹⁴ chapter 15, §5a, waste can be stored up to three years if it is intended to be recycled, before the storing will be viewed upon as a landfill and fall under legislation related to landfills. In the end, ReCreate partner Helsingborgshem, which commissioned the reuse pilot, could not see further use of the elements in their own building development within the three-year time frame. What is more, they were not able to quickly find any external parties who wanted to reuse them, and investing effort into searching for such parties did not fall naturally to the company's purpose as a housing developer. As a result, the elements were disposed of, not to risk violating the law. The legal aspect comes on top of economic implications of storing the elements, further complicating the already complex question of making the supply and demand of reclaimed elements meet. There are a number of examples from Sweden in recent years, where only few of all available elements from a deconstruction

¹² Regeringen. (2022). Uppdrag att utveckla arbetet med omställningen till en cirkulär ekonomi i byggsektorn. Fi2019/01146, Fi2022/00506.

<https://www.regeringen.se/contentassets/1142cf770563461eb4c5dbf2159b39f0/uppdrag-att-utveckla-arbetet-med-omstallningen-till-en-cirkular-ekonomi-i-byggsektorn.pdf>

¹³ [Masshantering och användning av massor i anläggningsarbete](#)

¹⁴ [Miljöbalk \(1998:808\) | Sveriges riksdag](#)

project could be reused at once, leaving plenty of elements behind, which then become crushed because of the situation above.

Despite dialogues with EPA, they have yet to provide further clarifications on potential options for how to interpret the waste status in relation to intended reuse of deconstructed precast concrete elements. In addition to the guidance on excavation masses¹³, the authority refers to the waste legislation and a flow chart to help determine the waste status¹⁵. Two vital legal paragraphs in this context are 1) the definition of waste from EU legislation: *'Waste is any substance or object that the holder disposes of or is required to dispose of'*, and 2) the definition of when waste ceases to be waste through *'preparation for reuse'*, which means *'controlling, cleaning or repairing something that is waste so that it can be reused without further treatment'* (Swedish Environmental Code, chapter 15, §6)¹⁶. To sum up, to support that more deconstructed concrete elements could be reused in new construction, it would be beneficial to re-examine how the regulation is interpreted. Deconstructed building elements with long technical service life could be interpreted as products instead of waste, even if the preparation for reuse has not been fully carried out and even if there is no known recipient or specific use yet.

3. 2. Developer's responsibility for property requirements

A central topic in the Swedish context and ReCreate partners' discussion, is the Swedish legislation's strong emphasis on the responsibility of the developer to prove compliance with legal requirements, including technical property requirements such as load-bearing capacity, stability, durability and protection pertaining to hygiene, health and the environment. As shown in Halonen et al. (2024: 18,41), there are three main concerns which are central to this discussion: the absence of established procedures for product testing and approval of reused products, potential emissions to indoor air, and restrictions for the presence of chemicals from the Regulation on the registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals (REACH) legislation¹⁷. From the viewpoint of the Swedish pilot and Helsingborgshem as its developer, the questions largely boil down to potential chemical analyses of importance for the developer to be confident that reused elements do not cause health risks for the users of the building, based on the responsibility of the developer as set in the Planning and Building Act¹⁸.

¹⁵ <https://www.kemi.se/stod-till-foretag/din-roll-och-ditt-ansvar/atervinnare-eller-anvandare-av-atervunna-material/produkt-eller-avfall---hall-koll-pa-skillnaden-sa-att-du-kan-folja-reglerna>

¹⁶ https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-och-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/miljobalk-1998808_sfs-1998-808/

¹⁷ [REACH Regulation - European Commission](#)

¹⁸ [Plan- och bygglag \(2010:900\) | Sveriges riksdag](#)

Procedures for product testing and approval

The absence of established technical standards for product approval, accepted by authorities, assigns a heavy responsibility on developers when it comes to proving the technical properties of reused construction products and components. At the time of the previous report (Halonen et al. 2024), no such guidance existed apart from what had been developed in a national sister project 'Återhus' ('Re-houses') (Brander et al., 2021; Gabrielsson & Brander, 2021), and in the meantime this discussion has intensified. The normal way for a developer to show compliance is to rely on product approval from a manufacturer or have to the building project contractor to guarantee product properties. However, at the end of the day, it is still the developer who is legally responsible for the compliance of the products and construction work. To scale up reuse, an established practice for the product approval of reclaimed precast concrete elements is, therefore, essential.

The Swedish ReCreate partners have had dialogues with all relevant national authorities (Boverket, the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, the Swedish Chemicals Agency and the Swedish Work Environment Authority) to understand the current regulation and how to test and approve reclaimed precast elements product properties with regard to content of hazardous substances. Although some matters were clarified, Boverket (2024) concluded that it is the industry's responsibility to develop guidance for the verification and approval of reclaimed construction products. This gives a lot of agency and power to the industry in an issue where some (linear) industry representatives may have an inherent incentive to hinder the circularity transition. Even though guidance has been requested by numerous actors, Boverket's stance is very much influenced by the large revision of the Swedish building regulations called 'the building rules of possibilities' which will enter into force in July 2025. A central discourse of these revised rules is to support innovation and a bigger variety of solutions by decreasing specific guidance by Boverket and to ensure that Boverket does not regulate more than necessary to meet with the requirements of the Planning and Building Act (2010:900), PBL¹⁹, and the Planning and Building Ordinance (2011:338), PBF²⁰. Nevertheless, Boverket did issue a guideline for reuse of load-bearing construction elements in the summer of 2024²¹. Unfortunately, the guideline is too general to support the product approval by the developer.

To move towards overcoming this problem, a project led by the Swedish research institute RISE, has been initiated. It aims to develop national guidelines for the quality assurance of load-bearing concrete structures for reuse. The intention is that the guideline could be used in future inspections and assessments of existing concrete structures intended to be reused. The project will be finalised in the end of June 2025. Members of ReCreate's Swedish country cluster from both KTH and Strängbetong form part of the reference group for the national project. At the time of writing the current report, it is not yet clear for which technical

¹⁹ [Plan- och bygglag \(2010:900\) | Sveriges riksdag](#)

²⁰ [Plan- och byggförordning \(2011:338\) | Sveriges riksdag](#)

²¹ Boverket (2024). Vägledning om återbruk av bärverksdelar. <https://www.boverket.se/sv/byggande/cirkular-ekonomi/vagledning/barverksdelar/>

properties the guideline will provide quality assurance guidance on. The intention is to differentiate guidance for four different element types: hollow-core slabs, precast concrete with prestressed reinforcement, precast concrete with non-prestressed reinforcement and in-situ cast concrete. Another intention is to follow the same rationale as the existing standard for reuse of structural steel (SIS, 2024), that is, to assign different quality assurance protocols based on the available information about the elements. This means that hollow-core slabs, with typically known provenance and more information available, would be assigned to follow a protocol with less testing needs, whereas in-situ cast elements typically would follow a protocol with more of testing requirements. The protocols would prescribe e.g. the extent of destructive full-scale testing. As in ReCreate's Work Package 4, the aim is to move towards a more cost-efficient quality assurance process that can be differentiated in relation to the type and origin of the element as well as the intended use of the element in a new building. In parallel with the development of this guideline, a Swedish standard for load-bearing precast concrete products for reuse has been developed in the SIS/TK 191²² committee, which is the Swedish mirror committee to CEN/TC229 Precast concrete products. It will be based on the Norwegian standard (Standard Norge, 2022; see also footnote 23) but will consider differentiation according to what is described above for the guideline project led by RISE. Additionally, it will contain advice about the calculation of service lives of the products, with the intention to clarify that it is rather the intended use that should guide e.g. what carbonation depth can be allowed. This stands in contrast to the reasoning in the Norwegian standard, in which a separate assessment of the remaining service life is required if the carbonation depth is higher than 10 mm. The standard cannot be used for CE marking, as for this purpose, a harmonized standard is needed, but it will still be an important step forward.

In the government commission on circular economy in the construction sector, Boverket (2024) also considered proposing the introduction of a producer responsibility for construction products. This would require producers to reclaim their products at end-of-life, which could incentivise *inter alia* producers of precast concrete elements to reclaim, refurbish, test, and approve reused elements for new sale. From the developer's perspective, this would be helpful as the developer would then be able to rely on the producer's approval in the same way as for virgin CE-marked construction products. In their work, Boverket (2024) suggests that Boverket and the Swedish EPA could be tasked by the government to investigate the conditions for a producer responsibility for certain product groups. Boverket states that product groups to primarily be considered include products with high turnover and/or high climate impact in production and large resource use. Precast concrete elements would seem to fall within this description.

Emissions to indoor air

As per the building regulations, the developer also needs to guarantee that the building and its components will not cause unacceptable risk to users' health. The way this is

²² <https://www.sis.se/standardutveckling/tksidor/tk100199/sistk191/>

²³ <https://standard.no/en/sectors/byggevarer/norwegian-standard-for-hollow-core-slabs-for-reuse--ns-3682/>

interpreted by Helsingborgshem and other Swedish building developers is to apply the so called 'rules of consideration' and the pre-cautionary principle embedded in the Swedish Environmental Code¹⁶. The aggregate in the concrete elements reclaimed for the Swedish reuse pilot contained moderate levels of Chromium VI. To scale up reuse, clarifications on conditions for reuse of elements with Chromium VI would thus be helpful to property owners and developers, when it comes to emissions to indoor air as well as to work protection when handling and cutting such elements.

REACH legislation

As described already in Halonen et al. (2024: 41), the Swedish country cluster received a clarification from the Swedish Chemical Agency that the limit values according to REACH restriction rules (ECHA, 2023) only apply to chemical products, such as cement. Reused concrete elements are rather defined as goods in the legislation. This was an important clarification for Helsingborgshem, since the aggregate of the reused concrete elements contained Chromium VI (mg per kg dry substance concrete) well above the limit value of cement in the REACH legislation.

3. 3. Reuse inventories in demolition permits

The lack of established routines on how to perform inventories of reusable construction products connected to demolition projects has also raised discussion among ReCreate's Swedish partners. The Swedish reuse pilot, the pavilion for the city fair H22 in Helsingborg in 2022, was designed and completed in a short timeframe in the very beginning of the ReCreate project. The ambition was to build the pavilion nearly completely of reused components. Therefore, extensive searches for donor buildings for reclaimed concrete elements were performed as part of the process. This proved highly challenging and therefore, the current lack of regulatory drivers to support inventories of components for reuse is of interest, as well as how such inventories could be compiled into searchable databases or marketplaces.

Due to new requirements being introduced to the EU Member States in the Waste Framework directive²⁴, provisions on the so-called 'control plan', which is a legally required document for a demolition permit, were updated in the Swedish Planning and Building Act (2010:900) Chapter 10 §6, in August 2020²⁵. The provisions state that in the control plan, the developer must identify which building products can be reused and how these should be taken care of. The motivation for the revised formulations in the Waste directive was to support more of selective demolition and deconstruction to enable the removal and safe handling of hazardous substances as well as to facilitate reuse and recycling of high-quality materials and products. However, some of the concrete elements reused in the

²⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32008L0098>

²⁵ https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-och-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/plan-och-bygglag-2010900_sfs-2010-900/

Swedish pilot were reclaimed in January 2020, that is, before the new requirement was introduced. Therefore, the potential for reuse was not something that had been considered in their control plan.

Since then, the interest for implementing reuse in general, but also for concrete elements more particular, has increased substantially in the Swedish construction and real-estate sectors. Thus, an access to reclaimed building products is also an increased concern in the industry. It would be critical to ensure that requirements for a well-performed inventory of potentially reusable building products (see also Vullings et al., 2022) are implemented and followed up by authorities.

The topic has been picked up by Boverket, which provides proposals in the final report of the government commission mentioned earlier²⁶, which was handed to the government in December 2024. In it, Boverket (2024) concludes that despite the strengthened link to support reuse through the regulatory change in 2020, the control plan is still not an effective tool to drive reuse, increased recycling, and waste minimisation. Boverket performed a review of control plans along with interviews to get an up-to-date picture on the implementation of the inventories. The results show that the changes made in the Planning and Building Act (PBL) in 2020 have not yet trickled down to practice. Control plans still focus on the inventory and handling of hazardous substances, whereas reuse is rarely covered.

Consequently, Boverket proposes to clarify the rules and guidance related to the control plan, in order for it to become a more effective tool in promoting reuse and linked sustainability targets. The proposal is to clarify the requirements in the PBL on the control plan by dividing it into two parts. The first part of the control plan is proposed to only entail the plan for ensuring technical requirements during the demolition/deconstruction. The second part is the plan for ensuring conditions for reuse, recycling and adequate waste management, a so-called 'resource management plan'. In Boverket's judgement, the division into two would also help to clarify authorities' responsibilities. The reuse inventories introduced in 2020 are controlled via the Swedish Environmental Code¹⁶ and therefore inspected by municipal environmental supervisors. However, the rest of the control plans are inspected by municipal building supervisors, who handle building and demolition permit applications and oversee the compliance with technical requirements in such projects. The introduction of a resource management plan should, according to Boverket, enhance cooperation and information sharing between the different municipal authorities and provide better conditions for increased reuse, recycling and waste minimisation.

To support a more efficient and a higher-quality process for both developers and the involved municipal authorities, Boverket further proposes that it should be commissioned to develop a centralised digital system in a common data environment for all involved parties. This would facilitate the information flow between actors when it comes to the control plans and demolition/deconstruction activities. In addition, Boverket suggest that it and the Swedish EPA develop a common national data environment to keep track of

²⁶<https://www.regeringen.se/contentassets/1142cf770563461eb4c5dbf2159b39f0/uppdrag-att-utveckla-arbetet-med-omstallningen-till-en-cirkular-ekonomi-i-byggsektorn.pdf>

resource and waste flows, and their management after demolition, built on the resource management plans. This is expected to improve control of waste streams, but also logistics for advancing reuse.

Discussions within the Swedish country cluster conclude that current inventories for reuse are still too vague and unspecific, and digital tools used for inventories do not consider structural parts like precast concrete elements. The digitalisation strategy suggested by Boverket could incentivise improvements, but better guidance and specifications for inventories are also needed. ReCreate's best practice proposals to this end are available in Vullings et al. (2022)

Finally, Boverket (2024) also proposes five new indicators to follow up the transition to a more circular building and construction sector. The most relevant indicator connected to scaling up reuse of precast concrete elements is 'material flows in and out of buildings'. A web portal is suggested for users to customise the monitoring of indicators for specific geographic locations, building types, time periods, etc. This also entails authorities collaboration to make the underlying data needed for such indicators available in the portal, which supposedly forms a better basis for connecting supply and demand of reused materials through, *inter alia*, marketplaces. Industry actors have also called for clear, sector-specific targets to further incentivise and speed up the transition. Boverket (2024) therefore recommends the government to task Boverket to develop such targets along with a national strategy for the sector transition.

4. The Netherlands

While planning to reuse the precast concrete elements reclaimed from the deconstruction pilot Prinsenhof in the Dutch reuse pilot, *Circulair Centrum Nederland* (CCN) building, the waste status of the reclaimed elements has emerged as important and elaborated on in this chapter (Section 4.1). Additionally, the permit process (Section 4.2) is discussed. Since the construction of the CCN building has not begun at the time of writing this report, the experiences discussed are mainly based on other similar projects by the ReCreate partner Lagemaat.

4.1. Waste status of reclaimed elements

It is necessary to determine whether the concrete elements meet the applicable environmental and health standards as specified in the Environmental Management Act (*Wet Milieubeheer*)²⁷. This law refers to the national waste management plan LAP3, in which the waste status is described.

Whether a material is considered as waste or not has to be first determined by the owner. As the first step, the owner must test the elements for the presence of hazardous substances, such as asbestos, heavy metals, or other harmful contaminants that could affect the safety of reuse. The results of these tests must be carefully documented and shared with the relevant authorities so that they can make an informed decision.

When submitting a deconstruction notification, the applicant is expected to present a detailed reuse plan. This plan should clearly describe the intended applications of the reclaimed materials or products, as well as the technical aspects of reuse. The plan should also evaluate the logistical aspects and environmental impact of reuse. It must demonstrate how the materials will be dismantled, stored, transported, and ultimately reused, ensuring that the process is both technically feasible and sustainable in the sense of the Dutch Environmental Management Act. The abovementioned aspects are included in the waste status assessment tool, to enable the determination of the waste status.

The Environmental Service as representative of the municipality (*Omgevingsdienst*) or other competent²⁸ authorities will thoroughly evaluate the submitted notifications and may impose additional requirements to ensure that the materials can be safely reused without

²⁷ <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0003245/2024-03-30/>

²⁸ In the Netherlands, the choice of the responsible authority can depend on various factors, such as the nature of the project, the location, and the specific laws and regulations that apply. For example, another competent authority may be chosen if it has more specific knowledge or powers relevant to the project. The choice can also be influenced by the administrative structure and responsibilities of different authorities. In some cases, the evaluation is conducted by an authority other than the environmental service, for example, if specific expertise is required that does not fall within the regular environmental services. This may be the case for larger infrastructure projects or situations where special legislation or environmental conditions apply.

negative consequences²⁹. This may involve taking extra measures to safeguard the quality of the materials or products or placing restrictions on the types of applications for which they can be used.

Once the notification is approved and the materials or products are deemed suitable for reuse, the materials or products can be further processed and applied to new construction projects. It is crucial that all steps in this process are carefully documented, and that ongoing monitoring takes place to ensure quality and compliance with the requirements throughout the entire value chain.

However, a complication to this process is that a broad range of authorities can accept or reject the determination of the waste status as done by the owner or another authority. In addition to the municipality, the province, the water board (*waterschap*), Human Environment and Transport Inspectorate (ILT, *Inspectie Leefomgeving en Transport*), Rijkswaterstaat, and finally the police and the justice department can have a say. The division of work between authorities is not straightforward; one authority can independently decide to examine the issue and impose a decision, even if another one has already examined it and taken a different stance. To our best knowledge, there are no obvious legal routes to solve such conflicts. For example, in ReCreate's Dutch deconstruction pilot in the city of Arnhem, no authority (municipal or other) stepped in to determine the reclaimed elements as waste. However, now that the elements are stored and waiting for reuse in the municipality of Heerde, the local authority could make a different determination. Also the province of Gelderland has the possibility to interfere with a different opinion. This brings about uncertainty to the process, especially because the waste status may not be formally determined during the process, therefore sometimes there is only an indirect determination of non-waste status.

4.1.1. Waste status assessment tool

The Dutch government has made available a waste status assessment tool³⁰ to support the determination. The tool is based on relevant legislation, case law, and policies as contained in the LAP3, and it is intended for use by both companies and authorities. After gathering all relevant information, a company can use the general assessment framework in the tool to make an initial assessment of the situation before the official decision by the authorities. It helps to apply the terms 'continued use', 'waste', 'by-product' and 'end-of-waste status' unambiguously in order to understand whether materials may need to be treated as waste, and what the potential consequences could be. This makes the process faster and more focused when the authority eventually makes a decision.

However, the final decision lies with the authorities, and it is necessary to wait for their approval before the project can proceed. The framework is therefore a preparation, but official approval is still required. Hereafter is summarised ReCreate company partner

²⁹ <https://www.omgevingsdienst.nl/omgevingsdiensten/> and <https://www.afvalcirculair.nl/afvalstof-of-niet-afvalstof/handreikingen/>

³⁰ <https://www.afvalcirculair.nl/afvalstof-of-niet-afvalstof/handreiking-afvalstof/>

Lagemaat's assessment of the waste status by following the evaluation steps of the assessment tool:

Step 1: Is the Material Classified as Waste?

According to the assessment framework, the first step is to determine whether the material can be classified as waste. In order to not to classify a material as waste, the following questions should all be answered with 'yes':

- Is the use of the material certain?
- Is the use of the material lawful?
- Is the use of the material of sufficient quality?

Lagemaat rationalizes that the elements from the Prinsenhof building were carefully dismantled with the explicit intention of reuse. The elements will undergo minor refurbishment (such as cleaning and applying a new coating), which, according to the guideline, does not mean they should automatically be classified as waste. They do not contain hazardous substances, so the reuse should be lawful. Reusing the elements limits the use of virgin resources and will not lead to adverse environmental or health effects, which should make the elements to meet the criterion of sufficient quality.

Conclusion from Step 1: It is likely that reclaimed concrete elements should not be classified as waste.

Step 2: End-of-Waste Route

If any doubt remains about the waste status, the end-of-waste route can be applied. Then, the materials must meet the conditions of the Environmental Management Act expressed in the guideline for the end-of-waste status³¹. These conditions are presented hereafter:

- Is there a specific purpose?
- Is there a market demand?
- Will the materials fulfill the technical requirements?
- Will the materials not have an unfavorable effect on the environment and health?

In this step, Lagemaat's rationale is the following. Should the reclaimed elements nevertheless be classified as waste, there is a demonstrable demand for circular construction materials, as exemplified by the Dutch reuse pilot. After the refurbishment, the elements and the materials will meet technical requirements for, among other things, strength, durability and health, verified through testing and inspections. Reusing the elements reduces CO₂ emissions and prevents waste production, so the impact on the environment is favourable.

Conclusion from Step 2: Should the elements nevertheless be classified as waste, the conditions for meeting the end-of-waste status can be shown.

³¹ <https://www.afvalcirculair.nl/afvalstof-of-niet-afvalstof/einde-afval/>

Step 3: By-Product Route

If the elements are considered to originate from a production process, i.e. if demolition or deconstruction is seen as such a process, it can be assessed whether the reclaimed elements would qualify as by-products. Then, the elements must meet the conditions of the Environmental Management Act expressed in the guideline for the by-product status³². These conditions are presented hereafter:

- Is it certain that the product will be used?
- Is there no need for further processing of the product?
- Is the product produced as an integral part of a production process?
- Will the use of the product not have an unfavorable effect on the environment and health?

The certainty of use and the need for further processing can be evaluated as in the previous steps. However, it is difficult to conclude that reclaimed products would be an integral part of a production process which was set up to create another product.

Conclusion from Step 3: Reclaimed elements can likely not be considered as byproducts.

Conclusion

Based on their evaluation using the self-assessment tool, Lagemaat classified the elements reclaimed in ReCreate's deconstruction pilot not to be waste. This provides a practical foundation for reusing the elements without the waste status in new circular construction projects. However, as mentioned before, the evaluation framework presented here is intended only as a tool for companies to make a preliminary assessment of the material status before the official decision from the authorities is made. Thus, this is an internal evaluation that can assist in preparation and planning, but the final decision always rests with the authorities. The final status of the elements will become clear through the permit process prior to the construction of the reuse pilot. Should it be needed, as per Lagemaat's assessment, the elements would meet the conditions for end-of-waste, too.

The authorities, after the official notification for construction is submitted, will determine whether the elements need to be treated as waste. If a company misjudges the status of the materials in the meantime, and the elements are later classified as waste by the authorities, this could indeed bring risks to the project. At worst, a company's meanwhile actions could be interpreted by non-compliance by the authorities. Less severely, introducing the end-of-waste process will have implications on the process duration. It is therefore important for companies to be aware that their preliminary evaluations are not binding and that the final approval and classification comes from the authorities. Due to the fact that several authorities can be involved in different stages of a deconstruction and reuse project, *inter alia* due to different geographical locations, chances are that different interpretations may be made by different authorities.

³² <https://www.afvalcirculair.nl/afvalstof-of-niet-afvalstof/bijproduct-route/>

4. 2. Building permits

Obtaining the building permit is a crucial step in the reuse process. Through the municipal authorities' handling of the building permit, it becomes determined that reuse complies with the applicable laws and regulations, and the building and its structure fulfill the requirements of the Building Decree (*Bouwbesluit 2012*, Bbl)³³.

The permit application done by Lagemaat for the construction of the CCN must comply with the Building Decree, and local and provincial legislation (see Halonen et al., 2024: 8-9), and include all relevant documentation required to justify the reuse of the reclaimed concrete elements. The application will include, among other things, also a free-form detailed reuse plan that describes the intended applications of the reclaimed elements, as well as the technical, logistical, and environmental aspects specific to reuse. The plan must demonstrate how the elements have been dismantled, stored, transported, and reused, ensuring the process is both technically feasible and sustainable in the sense of the Dutch Environmental Management Act, and that the element are not waste.

The Building Decree Bbl provides some flexibility in the assessment criteria when it comes to reuse, but it lacks specific criteria for reuse. ReCreate's Dutch cluster intends therefore, to rely on NEN 8702, a Dutch standard to assess the structural reliability of existing concrete structures. As additional permit documents, Lagemaat has developed detailed plans that address both the technical and aesthetic aspects of reuse. These plans will include, among other things, the Refurbishment Plan, Phasing Plan, Logistics Plan, and other documentation, which they include as an attachment to the permit application to demonstrate the careful approach.

When submitting the permit application, the relevant authorities will thoroughly evaluate the test results, certificates, and the reuse plan. The application will be assessed by the relevant municipal or provincial authorities, such as the Environmental Service (*Omgevingsdienst*), which may impose additional requirements to ensure that the reuse is safe and responsible. This may include requiring extra measures to safeguard the quality of the components or placing restrictions on the applications for which the concrete components can be used.

Lagemaat has held extensive discussions with the municipality and other relevant stakeholders in advance to identify and resolve potential issues and concerns in a timely manner. The aim is to anticipate and address concerns and minimise delays. As the first step, the Dutch reuse pilot's process includes a mock-up to test construction solutions first in small scale (a two-storey structure), for which a permit has been granted by the municipality of Heerde. Further learnings may arise once Lagemaat has fully navigated through the CCN's permit process under the authorities' guidance.

³³ <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/bouwregelgeving/bouwbesluit-2012>

5. Germany

The regulatory matters encountered in ReCreate's German pilots entail the waste status (Section 5.1) and building permits (Section 5.3).

5.1. Waste status of reclaimed elements

The German 'Act to Promote the Circular Economy and Ensure the Environmentally Sound Management of Waste' (Kreislaufwirtschaftsgesetz, KrWG)³⁴ of 2012 regulates and promotes, among other things, the circular handling of waste. The overarching aim is to conserve natural resources. The KrWG defines the rights and obligations of producers and owners of waste. A five-stage waste hierarchy sets out a clear procedure for the waste management. According to §6 KrWG it consists of (1) prevention, (2) preparation for reuse, (3) recycling, (4) other utilisation, and (5) disposal.

In practical terms, however, waste status in relation to the waste hierarchy only begins from the third stage, the recycling of waste. In other words, only from this point at which the owner of objects or materials actually disposes of them or wants or must dispose of them (§3[1] KrWG). Disposal is assumed when 'the holder transfers materials or objects to a recovery operation -- or to a disposal operation -- or relinquishes actual material control over them with the loss of any further purpose' (§3[2] KrWG). The building owner is responsible for defining whether reclaimed elements become waste or continue to be products. Should the owner transfer the ownership to a waste disposal company, the elements have unequivocally become waste.

By retaining the concrete elements in their entirety and with the intent for reuse, the waste status is avoided, and waste documentation (waste quantity reporting) is therefore not necessary. Though the authorities did not ask for waste documentation for the salvaged elements in either of ReCreate's German deconstruction pilots, individual decisions by authorities may occur concerning the necessity for waste documentation. A notification to the (waste) authority/environmental agency is in general only required if more than 10m³ of construction and demolition waste (C&DW) is present according to the Commercial Waste Ordinance (Gewerbeabfallverordnung, GewAbfV)³⁵. A hypothetical deconstruction, in which all concrete elements are reclaimed for reuse, would therefore not have to be reported to the environmental authority, as no waste would be produced. However, elements containing hazardous substances are not allowed to be reused. They become waste immediately after they are dismantled.

For the planned reuse pilot of a youth centre in Hohenmölsen, whose building owner is the town of Hohenmölsen, the managing director of the housing company WOBAU GmbH was contacted to clarify whether dismantled concrete elements from the donor building in

³⁴ <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/krwg/>

³⁵ https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/gewabfv_2017/

Otto-Nuschke-Straße 9-14 could be made available. The specialised company ECOSOIL Ost GmbH (a ReCreate industrial partner) was commissioned with the partial deconstruction. A partial deconstruction of the donor building was carried out, and out of the total number of dismantled concrete elements, 35% were found as suitable for reuse and were temporarily stored on the construction site, while 65% were pre-crushed on site and later processed into defined aggregates in a recycling plant. The temporarily stored concrete elements for reuse retain their product status and do not become waste because they have a continued specific purpose, unlike the concrete elements which were pre-crushed have become construction waste and must be assigned to the waste category in accordance with the KrWG.

The second German deconstruction pilot, located in Großräschen, also showcases the interpretation of the waste status. At the beginning of 2022, ReCreate industrial partner Ingenieurbüro Jähne was contacted by Bauinstandsetzungs-, Modernisierungs- und Erweiterungs-GmbH Senftenberg (BMA), a subsidiary of the owner of the donor building in Großräschen (KWG) to take part in the tender for construction supervision of the partial deconstruction and remodelling of the building on Karl-Marx-Straße. ECOSOIL GmbH was independently awarded the contract to carry out the partial deconstruction work. At this point in time, the senior site manager from ECOSOIL, Mr Gottschling, reached out to Prof. Mettke at BTU to get in contact with the building owner (KWG) to negotiate the reuse possibilities of reclaimed elements. Together with Prof. Mettke, Ingenieurbüro Jähne held several meetings to present the idea of reusing concrete elements to the building owner KWG. The aim was to gain support for the ReCreate project in order to prepare for a potential new reuse pilot project. This finally resulted in 90 elements being selected to be salvaged in the deconstruction process, which were intended to be used in a potential new pilot project and a test pavilion planned and executed by BTU.

In comparison to the deconstruction project in Hohenmölsen, the partial deconstruction and refurbishment project in Großräschen had a special feature: direct on-site reuse of some of the deconstructed elements. During the planning phase, it was decided – prior to the deconstruction of two and a half storeys – to carefully dismantle the roof elements, including the jamb wall elements (Drempel), and to reinstall them as the original roof once the storey deconstruction work had been completed. In other words, a so-called re-assembly was carried out on site. As these elements retained their intended use and remained on site they were not declared as C&D waste. The 90 concrete elements that were deconstructed with the intent to reuse on a different site did also not fall under the waste status in accordance with the KrWG, because intended 'further purpose' (also: continued intended use) was known at all times when the elements were deconstructed, moved, transported and stored. The 'further purpose' is shown through the plan to use the dismantled elements for a new building. This applies to both the potential second pilot project and the temporary test pavilion. However, the 12 elements used for the test pavilion had no further purpose after completion of the trial construction and were therefore subject to waste legislation and sent to a recycling plant for material processing accordingly.

5.1.1. Ownership and liability for reclaimed elements

To avoid the waste status for the used concrete elements in the sense of the law, their ownership has to be clear at any given moment. In general, the matter of reclaimed elements' ownership is regulated by the German Commercial Code (Handelsgesetzbuch), like with any other item or product.

The reclaimed concrete elements from the donor building in Hohenmölsen were transported from the deconstruction site to an interim storage facility on a designated site in the town of Hohenmölsen, owned by the town administration. All parties involved (Ecosoil GmbH, WOBAU GmbH and the town of Hohenmölsen) reached a consensus on the location, the required area, the storage conditions and any consequences of providing the interim storage facility in several agreements. Under German law, this constitutes what is known as 'implied action' (konkludentes Handeln), i.e. a tacit declaration of intent (stillschweigende Willenserklärung). There was however a written agreement made between WOBAU and City of Hohenmölsen that the set of concrete elements temporarily stored is made available to the town by WOBAU GmbH but remains their property until the start of the construction of the new youth centre. The agreement also notes that in the case that the construction of the youth center will not take place, WOBAU remains responsible for the disposal of the concrete elements. Here, the issue of ownership has been made explicit to define responsibilities in case the elements become waste.

The clarification processes for the second donor building of Großräschen, in particular about ownership and liability issues, led to a lively exchange between the lawyers commissioned by KWG, representatives of ECOSOIL GmbH, BTU, and a potential partner for a reuse project. As a result of the negotiations, KWG decided to provide the used concrete elements free of charge to a potential partner. The municipality of Kolkwitz (neighbouring the town of Cottbus) then provided an area for the temporary storage of the elements to facilitate a potential reuse pilot close by. As described before, the reuse of the dismantled elements was not part of the original planning and tendering phase of the building remodelling project in Großräschen. Therefore, no temporary storage area was planned on the construction site for the concrete elements intended for reuse. Due to a lack of space, a temporary 'special use permit' for the public footpath and parking pockets had to be applied for from the road traffic authorities to be able to temporarily store the elements directly in front of the dismantling site until they were removed. This three-month permit had to be extended twice, as both the removal date of the concrete elements and the planned test pavilion under supervision of BTU, for which 12 concrete elements were required, were postponed. Under business-as-usual circumstances (no reuse of elements), the additional space on the footpath and parking pockets would not have been necessary, as all elements would have been crushed on site, i.e. on the building's property.

The liability for the careful dismantling and careful reinstallation as well as the guarantee of the final conditions resulting from the work is the responsibility of the dismantling company. The liability for the integrity of the structural and physical properties as well as the durability and service life of the elements remains with the client/building owner, even if the client has commissioned third parties to clarify and confirm the required quality (assessment, static verification calculation, material tests). These matters are common legal frameworks in the construction sector, based on the 'Model Building Code'

(Musterbauordnung, MBO)³⁶, the 'German Civil Code' (Bürgerliches Gesetzbuch, BGB)³⁷ and the 'Procurement and contract regulations for construction services' (Vergabe- und Vertragsordnung für Bauleistungen, VOB)³⁸.

During deconstruction and temporary storage on the deconstruction site, the dismantled elements of the donor building in Großräschen were still the property of the client (KWG), because on the one hand, the elements had not yet been moved or transported by anyone other than the commissioned company (ECOSOIL GmbH). On the other hand, they were still the client's property, because the elements were still placed on the site of the demolition object or on the area specially requested by KWG. Once all the marked elements destined for potential reuse had been properly stored on the construction site, the planning for the construction of a test pavilion in Cottbus made from 12 concrete elements was finalised by BTU and the final storage location for the additional number of 88 additional concrete elements was secured and prepared on a communal area in Kolkwitz as mentioned above. The elements, which were previously the property of the client (KWG), became the property of the municipality of Kolkwitz with the beginning of the transport. Neither the dismantling company ECOSOIL nor the transport company that was commissioned had any liability or ownership rights to the transported elements. The 12 extra elements that were transported to Cottbus for the test pavilion became objects for scientific purposes for the BTU, but these elements technically remained the property of the municipality of Kolkwitz until they were disposed of.

5. 2. Building permits

In Germany, regulations for the construction of buildings are governed at the state level. The state building regulations are based on the MBO³⁶ – a set of rules that contains basic regulations for the construction and utilisation of buildings. The MBO specifies standard and minimum requirements. It serves as a standardised basis for the building regulations legislation of the 16 federal states, but it is not a directly applicable law in the federal states. The MBO contains directives, e.g. on planning permission, fire protection, safety, etc. When dealing with construction-specific objects that are to be used in or on the building, the MBO distinguishes between a *construction product* (Bauprodukt) and a *construction type* (Bauart). A *construction product* is a product, material or element that is manufactured to be permanently installed in a building, while a *construction type* is the combination of several *construction products* for the construction of a building.

To determine in which category used precast concrete parts intended for reuse are to be categorised, it is necessary to take a look at the MBO. This distinction is relevant regarding the applicable technical criteria. According to §17 MBO, a distinction must be made between regulated and non-regulated *construction products*. Regulated *construction products* are

³⁶ <https://www.bauministerkonferenz.de/suchen.aspx?id=762&o=7590762&s=musterbauordnung>

³⁷ <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bgb/>

³⁸ https://www.verwaltungsvorschriften-im-internet.de/bsvwwbund_31012019_BWI781063060120180001604634.htm

subject to the Model Administrative Regulation Technical Building Regulations (MVV TB, German 'Musterverwaltungsvorschrift Technische Baubestimmungen'³⁹, see also Halonen et al., 2024: 37) or bear a CE mark. They may be used in buildings if all requirements described in the relevant standards are met. Non-regulated *construction products* are those that are not covered by the MVV TB or other conventional standards. A non-regulated *construction product* is a product that deviates from the standards specified in the MVV TB and therefore requires a special certificate of usability. This can be either the *general building approval* (abZ, allgemeine bauliche Zulassung), the *general building approval test certificate* (abP, allgemeine bauaufsichtliche Prüfzeugnis) or an *approval in individual cases* (ZiE, Zulassung im Einzelfall). Both abZ and abP are certificates that the manufacturer of the *construction product* applies for from the German Institute for Building Technology (Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik DIBt), while the ZiE is a one-time certificate that can be applied for by the building designer, client or contractor from the highest building supervisory authority (Oberste Bauaufsichtsbehörde, in Saxony-Anhalt part of the Ministry for Infrastructure and Digital Affairs) in the respective federal state. In addition, according to §21 MBO, all *construction products* (except those with CE labelling) require confirmation of conformity either with the relevant technical requirements according to MVV TB or with abZ, abP or ZiE.

As with construction products, the construction types can be regulated (covered by the MVV TB) and non-regulated. If it is a non-regulated *construction type*, either the *general construction type approval* (aBG, allgemeine Bauartgenehmigung) or the *project-related construction type approval* (vBG, Vorhabenbezogene Bauartgenehmigung) can be issued. Here too, the *general construction type approval* (aBG) is more suitable for manufacturers of *construction products* that are to be used in a replicative assembled design and is issued by the DIBt, while the *project-related construction type approval* (vBG) is intended for individual cases and is applied for from the highest building supervisory authority of the respective federal state. In general, reinforced concrete (both in-situ concrete and precast reinforced concrete elements) is regarded as regulated, as it is covered by the MVV TB. Section A 1.2.3 of MVV TB lists all relevant standards and regulations for the manufacture and use of reinforced concrete in in-situ concrete construction and precast reinforced concrete components.

To determine which regulation applies to the ReCreate pilot projects in Germany and which authorisation is to be applied for accordingly, the first step is to clarify whether reusable precast reinforced concrete elements are *construction products* in the sense of standardised precast concrete elements or/and a *construction type* in the sense of the planned application in the pilot project in conjunction with masonry brick lining, timber stud walls and steel connectors. The relevant building authorities make a case-by-case decision on this question, as described in the following sections for each of the pilot projects. In

³⁹ https://www.dibt.de/fileadmin/dibt-website/Dokumente/Referat/P5/Technische_Bestimmungen/MVVTB_2023-1.pdf

addition, if the responsible building supervisory authority decides that the used precast concrete parts are not permissible in accordance with the requirements for regulated construction products or construction types, reference can be made to §16a Para. 4 and §20 MBO if no hazards are to be expected in accordance with the objectives of §3 MBO⁴⁰:

- the highest building supervisory authority can determine in individual cases that a building permit is not required (§16a, para. 4)
- the highest building supervisory authority may declare that consent is not required in individual cases (§20).

The first pilot project of the German ReCreate country cluster involves the construction of a youth centre in the town of Hohenmölsen in the federal state of Saxony-Anhalt, where the state building regulations of Saxony-Anhalt (BauO LSA, Bauordnung des Landes Sachsen-Anhalt) apply. The requirements for building products and types of construction in §§16-25 BauO LSA are strongly orientated towards the MBO (see Chap. 5.2.1). A few terms differ, but the regulations, as described above, apply unchanged. In September 2024, the planning team of the German ReCreate cluster met with representatives of the lower building supervisory authority in Weißenfels – responsible for the Burgenland district in which Hohenmölsen is located. In this meeting, fundamental questions regarding the procedure for obtaining planning permission for the pilot youth centre project were discussed. The building authorities confirmed that the planned building could in principle be authorised on the basis of the BauO LSA, as the construction project does not conflict with any public law regulations. However, it was strongly recommended that an appointment shall be made with the highest building supervisory authority of the state of Saxony-Anhalt in Magdeburg in order to clarify the secondary use of the used precast reinforced concrete elements. In the opinion of the lower building supervisory authority, a ZiE or vBG must be obtained, which must be issued by the highest building supervisory authority in Magdeburg.

This meeting in Magdeburg was held on 30 October 2024. Four specialist representatives from the highest building supervisory authority took part in this meeting. In the beginning, it was emphasised that the reuse of used concrete components was completely new territory in Saxony-Anhalt. It was therefore not surprising that the representatives of the highest building supervisory authority did not agree in some areas, which led to an intensive discussion. The stability expert explained, for example, that steel and concrete are regulated construction products (according to §§16-18 BauO LSA) and therefore do not require a ZiE or vBG. Only a confirmation from an independent external expert is required that the construction elements in question fulfil the properties required in the technical regulations. Another representative of the highest Building Supervisory Authority explained that it is not the construction product, but the construction type as a mixed construction of reinforced concrete, steel and timber that constitutes a deviation from the rules of construction technology. Yet another said that the problem to be solved was not proving compliance

⁴⁰ §3 General requirements: "Installations shall be arranged, erected, modified and maintained in such a way that public safety and order, in particular life, health and natural resources, are not jeopardised; the basic requirements for construction works in accordance with Annex I of Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011 shall be considered. This also applies to the removal of installations and when changing their use."

with the stability requirements, but compliance with the fire protection requirements. After an intensive discussion, the participants agreed on the following: The building permit procedure (responsibility lies with the lower building supervisory authority) must first determine what exactly the deviation from regulated construction products and types of construction consists of.

In addition to the question of the categorisation and approval of the used concrete elements, a so-called catalogue of criteria (in accordance with Section 65 (3) sentence 1 no. 3 BauO LSA41 in conjunction with Annex 2 of the Building Submission Ordinance) comes into play in the planning permission procedure. This catalogue is part of the building application and requires answers to questions about the structural design of the planned building. If a criterion in the catalogue of criteria is not met, the structural stability of the planned building project must be checked. This must be carried out by a test engineer for structural stability recognised by the highest building supervisory authority. The engineer is contracted by the authorities, though the expenses will fall on the applicant. These additional intermediate steps mean further time expenditure in the entire approval planning process. At the time of publication of this report, not all questions regarding the further authorisation procedure have been clarified. A final statement on the approval process will be published at a later date at a suitable point in the ReCreate project.

The second potential pilot project of the German ReCreate country cluster could include two smaller construction projects on the grounds of the local sports club SV Kolkwitz in the municipality of Kolkwitz in the federal state of Brandenburg. In this project, the authorization procedure for the use of used precast reinforced concrete elements should be very similar as described for the first pilot project, although here a different state building code applies, namely the Brandenburgische Bauordnung (BbgBO)⁴². The relevant paragraphs §§16–25 in the state building codes of Brandenburg and Saxony-Anhalt are practically identical with regard to contents, although some minor wordings are different, and some numbers of referenced annexes are varied.

Overall, the implementation of the relevant state building code regulations depends on the interpretation of the relevant laws by the lower (local) and upper (state) building supervisory authorities. In contrast to the first reuse pilot and due to a smaller project scale, it is envisioned here to apply for approval of the construction type with used concrete elements in parallel with the building permit. This means that the building authorities review the approvability of the building design (for the building permit) and determine the required procedure for the approvability of the construction product/construction type with regard to the reused concrete elements at the same time. This way the processes are more closely linked and could potentially be faster, but it also carries the risk that the building permit documents (i.e. the building design or construction details) will have to be amended and resubmitted according to the consequences arising from the authorities' position on the approvability of the used precast concrete elements and potential additional demands.

⁴¹ <https://www.landesrecht.sachsen-anhalt.de/bsst/document/jlr-BauOST2013rahmen>

⁴² https://bravors.brandenburg.de/gesetze/bbgbo_2016

6. How to improve legislation and administrative practices

This chapter discusses regulatory issues recurring in more than one country (Section 6.1) that would benefit either from clarification on the EU level to promote circular economy throughout the EU, or from the development of legislation and/or administrative practices at the country level – especially when waiting for a cross-EU regulatory solution. Furthermore, issues that arose in specific ReCreate countries (Section 6.2) but that would benefit from consideration on the EU level or by other countries, are also highlighted.

6.1. Issues recurring in multiple countries

6.1.1. Waste status of reclaimed elements

The waste status of reclaimed products and materials is one of the two topics that occurred in every country, along with reclaimed products' technical requirements and product approval (Section 6.1.2). The national legislation of each ReCreate piloting country, like that of every other EU country, is based on the EU's Waste Framework Directive²⁴ and the waste hierarchy it entails. However, the ReCreate pilots have shown that in practice, concepts and processes are clear at the lower levels (recycling, recovery, disposal) but remain ambiguous at the higher levels (waste prevention, preparation for reuse). This is noteworthy and highly problematic. The higher levels are supposed to be prioritised, but such prioritisation is impossible to achieve when so much disagreement and uncertainty pertains to core definitions and processes.

In Finland, the Ministry of the Environment provided a statement on reclaimed elements' waste status as per the Finnish waste legislation, following a request from ReCreate and a municipal environmental authority. The statement was highly helpful in providing clarity to the distinction between reuse as a form of waste prevention, and reuse that takes place after preparation for reuse. In the former case, reclaimed elements never become waste but retain their product status. This is the case – much like in the Netherlands and Germany – if their owner has not intended to discard them from use but has intentionally implemented a controlled deconstruction process that retains their use-value. In the latter case however, reclaimed elements have become waste, as by definition, preparation for reuse is performed on waste; the waste status ends once the waste has been prepared for reuse in such a manner that end-of-waste criteria have been achieved. Preparation for reuse implies a heavy remanufacturing process, akin to recycling. It is noteworthy that also reuse as a form of waste prevention can include refurbishment measures – it is just that the extent of these measures is more moderate. Therefore, simply the fact that some refurbishment is carried out, does not denote that the elements have become waste.

The interpretation of the waste status, as given in Dutch and German waste legislation, is largely similar, with the exception that the parties involved in deconstruction and reuse projects are themselves tasked with determining the waste status, without the support of a similar authoritative interpretation. Since reuse is still so rare and unestablished, and interpretations can vary wildly (as shown by e.g. the Finnish discourse), the lack of official guidelines or an authority's judgement on the waste status, provided ahead of time, remains a substantial risk for the companies involved. If a company misjudges the waste status and an authority steps in with a differing interpretation mid-process, an inadvertent breach of waste legislation can easily happen – with potentially devastating reputational consequences, not to mention the impacts on project schedules. The risks that presently result for the companies from the lack of established administrative practice when it comes to the waste status (and in case reclaimed products are interpreted as waste, also when it comes to the end-of-waste criteria) are a clear barrier to commercial upscaling of reuse. In the Netherlands, the issue is further complicated by the sheer number of different authorities that can potentially chime in independently, at any point.

What is more, an established interpretation of the issue can also form a barrier, as is the case in Sweden. Unlike in the other ReCreate piloting countries, the present Swedish waste legislation considers reclaimed elements always as waste. The legislation does not identify reuse as a form of waste prevention, but only as preparation for reuse. It enables the latter, but only when there is a known recipient within a fairly short time frame. Without a known recipient, the legislation has been interpreted to allow a temporary storage up to only three years before such storage is seen as an illegal landfill. In practice, this time frame often constitutes a barrier, since it becomes a risk – both legal and financial – to retain elements if no immediate recipient is identified. The time frame of three years would seem to have no clear substantive basis. Even though the other ReCreate piloting countries waste legislation is also based on the Waste Framework Directive, no such time frame exists in their legislation or interpretations thereof. Should reuse become mainstream, three years would likely suffice to find recipients in most cases (apart, perhaps, for construction sector recessions, which can last for several years). However, as reuse is currently only emerging, a blanket waste status and a short, arbitrary, non-substantiated time frame can act as effective barriers for upscaling. It is therefore recommended that the Swedish authorities reconsider these issues; inspiration for this can be found by looking at how they have been interpreted and justified in other countries. Apart from what has already been mentioned in the Finnish example, some potential ideas on this matter which aim to clarify the intention of the involved actors to reuse, include:

- Reclaimed concrete elements suitable for reuse have been identified in the control plan (or in the resource management plan if Boverket's 2024 proposal will be implemented into the regulation).
- Deconstruction is carried out so that the elements suitable for reuse, described in the control plan, are not damaged.
- Both deconstruction and temporary storage of elements entails costs and, therefore, implies the intention to reuse. This is also valid for temporary storage

on the property owner's own land, since a consequence is that this land cannot be hired out for other purposes.

However, a more ideal solution would be that the issue would be addressed at the EU level. One unambiguous definition for when reclaimed construction products become waste, as well as uniform end-of-waste criteria for different product groups (e.g. precast concrete elements), would help to ensure preconditions for commercial upscaling of reuse EU-wide.

6.1.2. Technical requirements and product approval of reclaimed products

Reclaimed products' technical requirements and product approval, whether part of a building permit or separate from it, is the other topic that arose in one way or another in every ReCreate piloting country. Currently, as seen from the report at hand, the product approval practices reused construction products are not firmly established in any of the ReCreate piloting countries. The product approval requires lots of negotiations and clarifications with the relevant authorities during a building project. The lack of established technical criteria and approval processes can lead to a situation where the requirements for product approval vary from location to location, or even project by project. This creates uncertainties and risks, not least since it implies ambiguity on associated costs and duration of test procedures, and therefore, reduces the willingness of companies to invest in developing circular solutions.

While waiting for an EU-level solution as a part of the CPR, which may take a long time to implement fully, it is crucial to develop the national practices towards being more systematic and predictable as processes. When it comes to suitable technical requirements, including those pertaining to indoor air quality and non-hazardousness, and a robust quality assurance process, the upcoming ReCreate deliverable D4.3, will provide best practice recommendations for reclaimed concrete elements. It is essential that the testing schemes are correctly dimensioned, as their underdimensioning could risk the health and safety of construction workers and building end-users, but overdimensioning could deteriorate the economic competitiveness of reuse vis-à-vis virgin products. Therefore, the quality assurance should not be a 'one size fits all' solution, but a nuanced approach is needed, where the testing requirements can be justifiably adapted to different stages for planning of reuse as well as according to the needs of different reuse applications.

ReCreate is not the only actor that has recognised this issue, though, and technical requirements are more generally seen as a problem by stakeholders. Stakeholders have thus started to work towards common practices in contexts external to ReCreate, too (e.g. in Sweden, the Återhus project, or in Finland, a project called UURAKET⁴³). However, such development projects – including ReCreate – have neither continuity after the funding ends,

⁴³ <https://www.rts.fi/project/uudelleenkayttavien-rakennusosien-kayton-edistaminen-talonrakentamisessa-uuraket-hanke/>

nor an authoritative position, like the government does. What is more, assigning all the agency to industry actors carries the risk that some entities will use such working groups as vehicles to hinder the circularity transition, since circular solutions may introduce competition to their current product portfolio and thus, not be in their genuine business interest. Although voluntary industry initiatives can be important and valuable, they cannot replace the role of governmental authorities (e.g. an organisation like Boverket in Sweden), who should take up the task of establishing common national product approval practices.

The lack of an established quality assurance process, with suitable technical criteria and clear product approval, also has its implications on value chain organisation and even the issue of liability. The lack of clear regulatory rulesets hinders the industry from organising into circular value chains, where replication of deconstruction and reuse could occur *en masse*. As a result, deconstruction and reuse typically remain as one-off projects for the parties involved. Thus, the projects do not get to benefit from prior experiences on relevant practicalities, including product approval, not to mention that the developer may have a limited interest or ability to implement both deconstruction and reuse in the same project. Furthermore, without functional industrial value chains and clear rules and processes, the issue of liability, i.e. who is responsible for reclaimed components' performance in case shortcomings arise, remains underdeveloped. Setting up clear technical requirements is helpful for clarifying for the roles and responsibilities of different involved parties (building surveyors, deconstructors, refurbishers, designers, builders) and forms the basis for voluntary certification systems pertaining to the 'best practice' execution of each profession's tasks. In this way, too, providing a clear legal framework can encourage circular industry reconfiguration and, eventually, contribute to more mainstreamed reuse.

6.1.3. Declaration of reclaimed components in demolition permits

The Finnish and Swedish country clusters both experienced that more attention should be directed at identifying reusable components in demolition permit processes. While ReCreate's Dutch and German clusters have not directly named this need, doing so could nevertheless help to resolve some of the issues around the ambiguity of the waste status and the associated uncertainty. Identification of reclaimed components in permits could have twofold benefits. First, it would help direct companies' and authorities' attention, in terms of the waste hierarchy, from the lower level of waste recycling towards the higher level of waste prevention. Second, it could be used as a means to control the quality of the planned deconstruction and in conjunction, officialise ahead of time the non-waste or waste status of the components to be reclaimed.

When it comes to the first point, it is noteworthy that while the responsibility for compliance with the waste legislation mostly lies with the waste management sector, the highest levels of the waste hierarchy (waste prevention and preparation for reuse) call for donor building owners to take action. According to observations of the ReCreate partners, the owners do not usually find themselves responsible for implementing waste hierarchy priorities. Taking the higher levels of the waste hierarchy seriously may require placing more obligations on building owners of potentially reusable building components, like the actions suggested in

Sweden. There, the introduction of a resource management plan and digitalisation and open sharing of its data in a common data environment to promote marketplaces and matching services, are deemed by ReCreate's Swedish cluster as important steps for further scale-up of reuse of precast concrete elements. However, it is important that Boverket, or jointly with the Swedish EPA, also further clarifies and provides more detailed guidance on the type of data required in those plans on materials and components relevant for reuse, preferably based on upcoming guidance from ReCreate's Work Packages 3 and 4 on data management and quality assurance. The Swedish country cluster also believes it is essential to speed up the development of the common data environment proposed by Boverket (2024), including formats to make the data easily accessible and transferable through open application programming interfaces (APIs) for all developers to further drive the scale-up of reused of concrete elements. What is more, ReCreate's Finnish cluster believes the provision of information should be mandated and not optional. This is in contradiction with the newly reformed Finnish Building Act, which entered into force at the beginning of 2025, where the declaration of reusable building components during the demolition of a building will be voluntary. Finnish members of ReCreate gave formal feedback for the legislator during the preparation phase of the Act that the Act will not have a sufficient steering effect towards the industry if it stays voluntary.

The second point stems from the experiences of the Finnish cluster but taps into some of the difficulties encountered by the Dutch cluster regarding the lack of official non-waste or waste status of reclaimed elements. In the Finnish deconstruction pilot, reusable building components did not have to be declared to the building inspection authorities when applying for the demolition permit although the law in force at the time (Land Use and Building Act Act 132/1999, 139§) required it: *'The permit application must explain how the demolition work will be organised and the conditions for dealing with the construction waste generated and the reuse of usable building components.'* This information was eventually provided, though to a different authority – the environmental one – during the discussions about the waste status (Section 2.1.). Therefore, in the Finnish case, it is proposed that in the future, the local environmental authorities should ask the building supervisors to require the information as part of the demolition permit application process. This practice would have the following benefits:

- *Ensuring the safety and quality of the deconstruction process.* Planned and structured operations are key to ensure the safety and quality of the deconstruction process. By requiring the information regarding the intent to reclaim components before the actual work begins, the authorities could promote the quality of the processes and ensure that a party undertaking a deconstruction project has the necessary capabilities.
- *Obtaining an authority's decision on the waste status.* During the ReCreate project, discussions and assessments of the waste status were not very systematic, and the issue evolved as the pilot project progressed in practice and the interpretations of the legislations got clearer (see Section 2.1.). This caused a lot of uncertainties and risks for the companies and other organizations during the pilot. As the matters regarding these issues got clarified a lot during ReCreate, the authorities would

have now an opportunity to systematise their practices in future cases by asking the applicants to provide the information that would allow them to decide already during the permit phase whether the dismantled components are to be classified as waste or not. This would create more established and predictable industrial practices that would decrease the risks for companies and, therefore, promote the development of a market for reusable building components.

6.1.4. Need for public incentives

All project countries agree it is important to scale up reuse in the construction sector. Most of the issues raised in this document, as well as those dealt with in the sector, are related to public sector actions and policies that aim to *enable* reuse in construction such as how to interpret legislations from the point of view of reuse, how the legislations should be changed to better take into account reuse, how the authorities should develop their practices so that reuse projects would be easier to execute, et cetera.

Difference nonetheless can be shown when it comes to the tools of governance that should be used. These may to some extent national traditions and availability of existing policy. Furthermore, implementing new solutions is always more costly compared to the existing products due to inefficient and underdeveloped work practices, unestablished supply/value chains, and learning and testing required. Consequently, innovative circular solutions can hardly compete with the existing solutions in sufficiently large scale and, thus, the public incentives are needed in order to scale up the solutions in the industry.

In this vein, the Finnish land allocation competition is an example of an existing policy instrument of the local authorities, that was extended to include circular criteria. The competitions and criteria developed in ReCreate and presented in this document are one way to create such incentives in a municipal level, but the public sector organisations should create policies in multiple governance levels. Similarly, the Dutch Prinsenhof project was based on a tender by the province of Gelderland which included circular criteria. Also the German cluster recommends that public procurement policies could prioritise projects that demonstrate significant use of reused materials, setting a precedent for the private sector. Implementing such incentives would not only promote environmental sustainability but also stimulate innovation within the construction industry. The Dutch cluster recommends preferential public procurement.

However, in the future, policymakers should begin to lay down policies and initiatives that create *incentives* for companies to develop circular solutions. In all likelihood, to encourage the adoption of reused materials, financial and regulatory incentives are necessary. This could, as the Dutch and German clusters recommend, involve subsidies or tax benefits for projects that incorporate reused components, making them more economically attractive.

6. 2. Country-specific issues

6.2.1. Qualification requirements of designers

The issue of experts' qualification requirements in deconstruction and reuse projects arose in Finland, as one of the matters its construction legislation addresses concerns qualification requirements for designers in a construction project (see Halonen et al. 2024: 43). The requirements vary according to the difficulty and type of design tasks. The legislation does not currently acknowledge circular construction tasks, but as argued in Halonen et al. (2024:44-45), reuse-related tasks should most likely be classified as one of the highest difficulty level design tasks as such *'design work requires the use of novel or otherwise highly demanding design, calculation or dimensioning methods in an approach which is experimental or unique in other ways, and on which there is no experiential knowledge available. Examples: experimentations with construction materials, such as innovative timber construction; experimental zero or plus energy buildings'*.

In ReCreate's case, the design team encompasses Finland's leading experts on service life of existing structures. Perhaps because the involved experts were reputable and known to be highly qualified (PhDs and university professor level), the authorities did not ask about their competences during the pilots. However, in commercially driven projects, qualifications may come into play more so than in a high-expertise project like ReCreate. As deconstruction and reuse project are challenging to execute and require new ways to plan and manage construction processes, in future building supervisors should lay down at least some qualification requirements to ensure high-quality results. What is more, reuse requires expertise not only from structural engineers but also architects, and it seems this fact is not presently well understood, as some stakeholders see reuse exclusively as a structural engineering question (which it is not, as successful reuse is also connected to the smart organisation of existing elements into functional spaces, requiring architectural effort). Unlike those of structural engineers, architects' qualifications are to a degree regulated at the EU level, potentially offering possibilities for EU-wide proficiency requirements in circular architectural design.

In the light of the experience gained from the pilot projects, legislators should also assess whether qualification requirements should be extended to professions other than designers. For example, in the process of quality assurance and product approval, qualified experts are indispensable. The survey of elements' condition and properties set the scene for the success of the whole reuse process. It is therefore vital that elements are assessed by competent and experienced people, while currently, there are no formal proficiency requirements for experts undertaking such tasks.

6.2.2. Producer responsibility of manufacturers

The issue of producer responsibility of construction product manufacturers was brought up in Sweden and, to a lesser degree, in Germany. In Sweden, Boverket (2024) has suggested that Boverket and the Swedish EPA could be tasked by the government to investigate the conditions for a producer responsibility for certain product areas. In particular, building products with high production greenhouse gas emissions are highlighted as important to consider. Concrete elements certainly fall under this definition. If well designed, such a producer responsibility would have a potential to incentivise the development of industries to take care of, recondition, and sell reclaimed precast concrete elements for reuse in new

constructions. It would therefore be important to investigate how such a producer responsibility could be designed and what consequences it could have. In a large government commission in 2001, the investigator concluded that it would be beneficial with a legal producer responsibility for the building sector, but that the voluntary sector commitments would still be good to follow for a number of years through the new action plan delivered by the building sector's eco-cycle council at that time⁴⁴. Considering that much time has passed since then and that partly other environmental issues were in focus in that commission, it seems to be relevant to commission the investigation suggested by Boverket.

Concrete elements are no different in terms of their environmental burden in other EU countries, so the idea of a producer responsibility could lend itself to an EU-wide implementation. However, an obvious challenge in the context of construction products that the lifetimes of buildings tend to exceed those of companies that manufactured their parts. For instance, the two German donor buildings were constructed in the former GDR. With the fall of the Berlin Wall and reunification of Germany, many companies, including the manufacturers of those prefabricated concrete elements, were dissolved. In this and likely in most other cases, it would not be possible to return the reclaimed concrete elements to the original producer. Therefore, such a producer responsibility should not be tied to who originally manufactured the products. Instead, the duty to take back should rather concern the product category that a manufacturer produces.

6.2.3. Climate regulation incentives

The urgency of climate change presently constitutes a prominent driver for the increased interest in reusing precast concrete elements, due to the embodied carbon saving potential. In ReCreate, the issue arose in Sweden, but the situation is no different in other EU countries. In the Swedish context, mandatory climate declaration regulation⁴⁵ is an incentive to this direction, while the recast of the Energy performance in buildings directive (EPBD) (European Parliament, 2024) is now driving the development of such regulations in all EU member states. To strengthen the incentives, Boverket (2023) proposed to introduce limit values for maximum embodied carbon for new buildings in Sweden, to take effect in 2025. However, the initiative has been postponed⁴⁶ and will likely rather follow the timeline according to the EPBD recast. The present climate declaration regulation in Sweden implies that reused construction products can be assigned zero climate impact, as a simplification to promote reuse⁴⁷. It is therefore important that the government fulfils the intention to introduce strict enough limit values in the regulation as soon as possible, to further provide

⁴⁴ [Resurs i retur – Slutrapport från utredningen för översyn av producentansvaret | lagen.nu](#)

⁴⁵ https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-och-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2021787-om-klimatdeklaration-for-byggnader_sfs-2021-787/

⁴⁶ [Nytt regeringsuppdrag till Boverket om gränsvärden för byggnaders klimatpåverkan – Klimatdeklaration – Boverket](#)

⁴⁷ Dataset for 'reused construction product' (återanvänd byggprodukt) in Boverket's climate database with generic data to be used for the regulated climate declaration of new-build, if environmental product declarations (EPDs) are not used: [Boverkets klimatdatabas – detaljer](#)

incentives for reuse. A similar regulatory initiative (the introduction of limit values) is ongoing in Finland, too. In addition to this, the fulfilment of the planned sharpening of the EU Emissions Trading System (EU-ETS)⁴⁸ is important to further encourage reuse. It has the power to change cost structures in construction that most likely will incentivise increased reuse of concrete elements throughout the EU.

⁴⁸ [EU Emissions Trading System \(EU ETS\) – European Commission](#)

7. Conclusions

This report has reviewed how legislations and other norms have been applied in practice during ReCreate's pilots, and how regulation should be developed in the future to better enable the development of circular solutions in the construction sector. As mentioned in the introduction, the document took a national focus for the analyses. This was because the regulations most relevant for reuse are presently in national control. Nevertheless, the report's observations can feed the development of regulation on the EU-level, too. For example, ReCreate's experiences on the product approval processes of reused components in different countries (including sufficient level of technical testing) can inform the EU CPR.

The main take-away from the report is that although there are some differences in policies and administrative practices, the same themes and issues are largely repeated across countries. There is a need to clarify interpretations of legislations (e.g. waste legislation), to make permit applications and product approval predictable with clear criteria and processes, and create public incentives for companies for circular development. Because of these similarities, there are also many opportunities for future cooperation between EU countries when developing national policies. As the main goal of this document was to provide a practical outlook into the legislative issues, the findings of the document are summarized from two operative perspectives: what should a company take into account when planning reuse project (Section 7.1), and how reused solutions could be scaled up in construction industry (Section 7.2).

7.1. What should a company take into account when planning a reuse project?

The ReCreate cases presented in this document highlight the amount of interaction and negotiation required in reused projects in comparison to normal construction processes. This results from the lack of established practices. As also described in Jonker-Hoffrén (2023), stakeholders must reach consensus and agreement on these matters via negotiations that are normally handled, for example, by following standards or regulations (e.g. the CPR). Most of these discussions were related to the interpretation of waste status and required environmental permits, or the product approval as part of building permit applications and relevant technical criteria.

Due to the lack of technical standards for reuse, extensive tests were carried out by ReCreate members on reclaimed elements to show to authorities that the elements are technically sound and safe to use. This, of course, was also one of ReCreate's purposes as a research and innovation project, and the work will eventually contribute a best practice proposal on the sufficient level of testing that could be incorporated in the CPR. In the meanwhile, however, while such standards are still due, it may not be clear to parties of a reuse project how extensive testing will be required by authorities, even if prior negotiations

on the issue are held. Therefore, future construction projects that seek to make use of reclaimed building components should pay attention to these issues, as they require financial and human resources, a new kind of expertise, a different approach for stakeholder interactions, and sometimes even pose significant challenges in terms of timeframes compared to conventional construction projects. The previous report (Halonen et al. 2024) gives an idea of which pieces of regulation could theoretically come into play, while the current report indicates which statutes have proven controversial in practice during ReCreate and gives examples how to navigate negotiations pertaining to them.

7. 2. How to scale up reuse in construction industry?

ReCreate's pilots show how industry (permit application) practices are currently based on local negotiations and case-by-case consultations with relevant authorities. Due to the fact that practices, demands, and interpretations of legislation usually vary among authorities, the current situation causes uncertainty for companies and, consequently, decrease the willingness to invest in developing circular solutions. Thus, it is crucial to develop established EU-level and national guidelines for administrative practices and policies. Predictability is a key to ensuring preconditions for scaling up circular solutions in the EU construction industry.

Of course, many member states have already started to work towards these goals. There are good examples from the ReCreate countries on the initiatives that aim to harmonise practices. For example, the Netherlands has a national guideline that helps to assess whether deconstructed elements should be considered as waste (see Section 4.1.1.). In Sweden, a recent and large national commission (Boverket, 2024) provided proposals to enable the transition to a circular economy in the construction sector. These include, for example, digitalisation proposals and potential regulatory changes which may support scaling up the reuse of concrete elements. In Finland, building inspectors have set up an informal cooperation network (TopTen), which aims to harmonise building inspection practices related to, among other things, the product approval of reused building products. All the examples contribute towards scaling up circular solutions, and there are plenty of learning opportunities between countries to this end. However, as the cases presented in this paper also show, many uncertainties still severely hamper the mainstreaming of circular solutions and, thus, there is much work to be done to streamline administrative procedures.

However, establishing clear criteria and predictable processes is just a start. In most policy-related debates, including this report, the focus has largely dwelled on how legislation and administrative practices can *enable* circular solutions by developing the current practices. At the same time, it is lucid that new circular solutions have a hard time being competitive to virgin materials because the current industrial value chains, knowledge and expertise, production methods, markets, etc. are established on basis of virgin production and do not support the introduction of circular solutions (see also Huuhka et al., 2023). Therefore, public

incentives (e.g. tax reliefs, preferential treatment in public procurement or in land allocation processes) are also required to the level the playing field. During early stages of market formation, incentives can help circular construction solutions like reuse to compete more fairly with linear solutions, which benefit from their established position, following from decades of use and hyper-optimisation of production and market conditions. Without public incentives that encourage industrial stakeholders to establish value chains and generate competences around circular construction, most companies are not easily able to justify investments into circular technologies from a pure business point-of-view.

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